

GAME-BASED TEACHING – A ROAD TO ATTRACTIVENESS OF AN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

Gamification has been developing as a megatrend in higher education for the past decade [10, 5]. The increasing digitalization and individualization of learning leads to the need for didactic and technological educational innovations that can enormously increase the attractiveness of higher education institutions [11]. Gamification is one solution for ensuring attractive, sustainable higher education teaching. This is based in particular on the effects that can be created by a playful learning environment and its elements: Increased learner motivation and engagement as well as learning efficiency are results of international studies that have investigated the effects of gamification in educational contexts [4, 5, 14]. By using gamification in education the following goals could be achieved: increasing (learning) motivation, the promotion of different types of knowledge and the acquisition of skills and competences [26]. On this basis, it is possible to implement game-based elements in various subject disciplines of higher education. In doing so, learning processes are combined with game design elements so that a modified version of the learning process is perceived by learners as game-like [15]. The mere implementation of game elements in learning settings is not enough. The focus is on linking game design and pedagogical principles [11]. Some studies also establish a connection between various game design elements and Ryan and Deci's self-determination theory [18, 24, 25]. This states that there are three universal, basic psychological needs that influence human action: Experience of competence, experience of autonomy and experience of social inclusion.

In their research, Bai et al. (2020) were also able to identify the following four positive aspects that students associate with gamification: It promotes enthusiasm, enables direct feedback on one's own performance, can fulfil a need for recognition and promotes goal achievement.

Escape games, which focus on collaborative, playful learning, offer a particularly innovative type of gamification approach in the educational context [6]. Escape games are defined by Nicholson [21, p. 1] as "live-action team-based games where players discover clues, solve puzzles, and accomplish tasks in one or more rooms in order to accomplish a specific goal (usually escaping from the room) in a limited amount of time". Initially developed as a leisure activity, educators have recognized its enormous potential for use in educational contexts, making it one of the central formats in current game-based learning discussions [3]. Educational Escape Rooms (EER) foster valuable skills such as teamwork, leadership, creative thinking, time management and communication [28]. The scope of application of EER currently extends particularly in STEM studies and healthcare, where the generation of specific skills that can be taught through game-based elements is central [23, 29]. In entrepreneurship education, Educational Escape Rooms have so far been rather less common, although the importance of entrepreneurial skills and serious games is undisputed in entrepreneurship research [19, 27]. Moreover, entrepreneurship education shows parallels to education in STEM fields, as solving real-world problems (for example, through new business models or product innovations) is a central feature [7]. A lack of existing, already evaluated game design elements can be listed as a reason for the deficient implementation of Educational Escape Rooms in Entrepreneurship Education [17]. In order to counteract this lack, it is of central importance to develop one's own Escape Games that are oriented towards current learning content. One model that can be used as a basis for conception is the Star Model. It was developed to highlight the components of a game design concept for EER. These serve as a basis for developing EER regardless of the discipline. The model takes into account five game elements, which are based on the star in the centre, and four context elements, which are found as a framework model around the star [3]. The five inner elements determine the design of the game, while the outer context elements should be analyzed and determined before designing the game, as they influence the game elements.

In the entrepreneurship field, Martina & Goeksen (2020) have elaborated eleven design elements in which the competences to be promoted are combined with gameplay elements.

Figure 1: Star Model for Educational Escape Games (Botturi & Babazadeh, 2020).

This structure can be applied to various Escape Games for implementation in university teaching. For the development of the Escape Game, it is essential to provide individual puzzles that build on each other linearly and fit the given topic stringently in terms of content. A list of possible Escape Game building blocks such as riddles, puzzles etc. is available online (e.g. at <https://escaperoomspiele.com/escape-room-raetsel-typen-und-ideen/>). Teachers can creatively adapt these ideas to their topic and the associated learning objectives. In addition to games that are played haptically, digital escape games in particular support the development towards digital and innovative university teaching. To this end, it is essential to use a platform that allows for the digital implementation of linear gameplay and different types of puzzles. In addition to developing apps and websites, it is possible to create Power Point presentations, PDF documents or e-books that build on each other and contain various links or media such as audio or video.

Table 1

Design Elements for Educational Escape Rooms for Experiential Entrepreneurship Education (Martina & Goeksen, 2020).

Design Elements for Educational Escape Rooms for Experiential Entrepreneurship Education			
Competences	References	Gameplay	References
Cooperation	Johnson & Johnson, 1981	Narrative	O'donovan et al., 2013
Spotting oppertunities	Bacigalupo et al., 2016	Increasing difficulty	Ericsson, 2008
Self-awareness and self-efficacy	Bacigalupo et al., 2016; Bandura, 1977	Immediate feedback	Nah et al., 2014
Initiative, motivation, and perseverance	Bacigalupo et al., 2016; Vygotsky, 1978	Hint management	Lopez-Pernas et al., 2019
Financial and economic literacy	Amagir et al., 2018; Bacigalupo et al., 2016	Time limit/ countdown clock	Kapp, 2012
		Game rules	Jambhekar et al., 2019

Application in teaching (at South Westphalia University of Applied Sciences)

In the winter semester, students in the third semester of the Bachelor's program in International Management with a focus on Entrepreneurship developed digital Escape Games. The task was to develop a game that depicted a real business model, which had to be innovated in parts or as a whole in order to remain in existence in the long term.

The central learning objectives in the seminar were as follows:

1. the students deepen the basics of business modelling by applying the Business Model Canvas to real examples;

2. the students learn to analyze business models and to understand and link problems with the help of the Design Thinking approach;

3. the students are strengthened in a playful way in the entrepreneurship competences and motivated for in-depth contents.

The students developed digital Escape Games in small groups of 2-3 students and presented them in a circle training. The learning objectives pursued, the story, the connection to the business model and the creative, technical implementation were used as assessment criteria. In the evaluation of the students, the promotion of the entrepreneurship competences found in the Goeksen set-up became very clear. The results were highly versatile and creatively implemented.

In the expert talk, the relevance of game-based learning for the attractiveness of the university is made clear, and examples and recommendations for action are used to show how the concrete implementation can be designed.

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Mittelstädt Ewald, Pütz Lisa-Maria. Гейміфікація освіти – шлях до підвищення привабливості навчального закладу.

Автори торкаються питання дидактичних та технологічних інновацій в освіті, яких потребує сучасне цифрове освітнє середовище, та зосереджують свою увагу на гейміфікації як інноваційному підході, що сприятиме ефективності та привабливості вищої освіти. Автори детально розглядають переваги гейміфікації та її позитивний вплив на результати освіти. Серед переваг визначаються: розширення спектру навичок та компетентностей, які можна отримати в результаті навчання, активніша участь студентів та підвищення їхньої мотивації. У роботі автори звертаються до наукових досліджень за темою, в яких йдеться про необхідність поєднання принципів гри та педагогіки, та обґрунтовується застосування навчальної гри як діяльності, що задовольняє такі базові психологічні потреби людини, як потреба відчувати свою компетентність, самостійність та соціальну інклюзію (приналежність).

У даній роботі автори зосереджуються на конкретному інноваційному типі навчальних ігор, а саме на квесті, який визначається як «командна гра, учасники якої знаходять підказки та докази, розв'язують завдання та загадки за обмежений час для досягнення певної мети (отримати перемогу, вийти з лабіринту, тощо)». Автори бачать значний потенціал квестів в освіті підприємців, де вирішення реальних проблем (через створення нової бізнес-моделі або інноваційного продукту) є центральним завданням. Недостатня кількість існуючих та апробованих ігрових елементів, розроблених для освіти підприємців, автори вважають головною причиною обмеженого використання квестів. Тому важливим завданням викладачів вони вважають створення власних квестів, які б відповідали актуальному змісту освіти.

Ключові слова: цифрове освітнє середовище, гейміфікація, квест, структура гри (гейм-дизайн), освіта підприємців.

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The paper deals with the need for didactic and technological educational innovations in digital education environment, suggesting gamification as a solution for insuring attractiveness of higher education institution. The authors look into the advantages of gamification and its positive impact on learning efficiency, among which acquisition of a wider range of skills and competences, increased learners' engagement and higher motivation. The paper refers to academic works that highlight the importance of linking a game design with pedagogical principles, and prove that gamification as an approach meets three universal, basic psychological needs that influence human action: experience of competence, experience of autonomy and experience of social inclusion.

The paper focuses on a certain innovative type of education games – escape games defined as “live-action team-based games where players discover clues, solve puzzles, and accomplish tasks in one or more rooms in order to achieve a specific goal (usually escaping from the room) in a limited amount of time”. Escape games are considered to have great potential in entrepreneurship education where solving real-world problems (for example, through new business models or product innovations) is a central task. A lack of existing, already evaluated game design elements can be listed as a reason for the deficient implementation of Educational Escape Rooms in Entrepreneurship Education. In order to counteract this lack, according to the authors, it is of central importance to develop one's own Escape Games that are oriented towards current learning content.

Key words: digital education environment, gamification, escape games, game design, entrepreneurship education.